

Pattern of Referrals to Psychiatrist in a Multi-specialty Tertiary Hospital in Nigeria: A Retrospective Study

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ABSTRACT

Background: Referral pattern to psychiatric services is inadequately documented in Nigerian tertiary hospitals. Consultation-liaison psychiatry (CLP) plays a crucial role in integrating mental health care in tertiary care hospitals. **Objectives:** To assess the pattern of referrals to a psychiatry department from other specialties in a Nigerian teaching hospital. **Methodology:** This cross-sectional retrospective study examined the referral patterns to the psychiatry department at Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital Nnewi, Nigeria, over a two-year period (June 2nd, 2022 - June 5th, 2024). Data from 263 in-hospital referrals were analysed using SPSS version 23. Information obtained included referring department, sub-specialty involved, reasons for seeking psychiatric consultation and psychiatric diagnosis. **Results:** The study revealed that nearly half (46.8%) of referrals were from Internal Medicine and Surgery (27.4%), with frequent requests originating from Neuro-surgery and Cardiology sub-specialties. The majority of referrals were prompted by irrelevant speech (35.7%) or disturbing behaviours such as restlessness (24.0%) and aggression (17.9%). Schizophrenia/psychosis and major depression were the most commonly diagnosed conditions. Notably, 57.0% of referrals did not specify a psychiatric diagnosis. **Conclusion:** There is a potential under-utilization of CLP from other specialties, and challenging behaviours was the major reason that prompts psychiatry consultation. This underscores a critical necessity for increased awareness of other psychiatric signs and symptoms, and integration of psychiatric services throughout all medico-surgical subspecialties.

Keywords: Pattern, Referrals, Consultation-liaison, Psychiatry, Specialties.

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INTRODUCTION

Consultation-liaison psychiatry (CLP) has emerged as a new sub-specialty in psychiatry, which deals with the relationship between physical diseases and mental ill-health.¹ It provides a holistic care of a sick person by adopting a biopsychosocial model of care that comprises the interplay of physiological, psychological, and sociological care in ill-health.² In tertiary care hospitals, there is a service communication between specialities in the course of managing or treating a sick person to ensure optimum and comprehensive healthcare delivery, on which basis CLP exists. In fact, it is a set up where the psychiatrists are involved in the medical and surgical team care.

Approximately 22.0% and 17.4% of inpatients in the general adult medical and surgical emergency wards respectively, suffer from some kind of psychiatric disorders.³ Specifically, among the elderly, there is at least 35.0% probable psychiatry morbidity among elderly patients in medico-surgical wards.^{4,5} The association between chronic physical illness in children and the emergence of behavioural-emotional problems has been reported in literature as well.⁶ About 1 in 5 adolescents experiences a mental health problem in a given year.⁶

Despite the increasing number of patients with mental health problems in a general medical/surgical care, the rate of consultation requests for psychiatrist evaluation and management remains low.⁷ Evidence showed that most of the few referrals to psychiatrists were from the department of Internal Medicine.^{8,9} Some physicians do not refer their patients to CLP due to concerns regarding potential stigmatization, despite being reported by patients that having psychiatrists integrated in their care team have been beneficial.^{10,11}

We posit that the findings of this work will serve to inspire medical professionals across various specialties, particularly those who have not yet utilized CLP, to aid their patients who may require psychiatric services. It will also be an evidenced-

based eye-opener to hospital management and policymakers, in understanding the level of utilization of CLP across all sub-specialties of medicine, and support tailored interventions to enhance consultation-liaison psychiatry.

Most of the works on the referral pattern to psychiatrists were conducted in developed countries, while there is paucity of such research in Africa, particularly in Nigeria. Therefore, we aim to evaluate the pattern of referrals or consults to a psychiatry department from other specialties in a Nigerian teaching hospital.

METHODOLOGY

Study Design

This was a cross-sectional retrospective study.

Source of Data and Study Setting

Data were obtained from all 263 in-hospital hard-copy referrals sent to the psychiatrist from other departments in Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital Nnewi, Nigeria over a period of 2 years (June 2nd, 2022- June 5th, 2024). We extracted data such as the socio-demographic profile of the patient (age and gender), the referring department, the subspecialty involved, reason(s) for the psychiatric consult and the psychiatric diagnosis made in the referral etc.

Ethical Approval

The ethical approval was obtained from Anambra State Ministry of Health Research Ethics Committee with protocol number: ASMOHREC/2024/15062024/17. The study was conducted according to the Helsinki declarations on ethical principles for medical research involving human subjects.

Data Management

Data was analyzed using the statistical product and service solutions (SPSS) version 22 (IBM Chicago IL, USA) and shown in the frequency distribution.

RESULTS

Nearly half (n=123; 46.8%) of the referrals to the psychiatrists in the hospital came from the department of Internal Medicine, followed by the Surgery Department (n=72; 27.4%) as shown in Table 1. Neuro-surgery and Cardiology were the most frequent sub-specialties that sought the service of the psychiatrist (n=26; 9.9% and n=25; 9.5%, respectively as seen in Figure 1. The referring clinicians did not specify the sub-specialty that requested the service of the psychiatrist in at least one-fourth of the consults.

One in four (n=66; 25.1%) of the consultation-liaison referrals was requested within 3 days of the patient having consultation with the referring doctors (Table 2). Confusion (n=38; 35.7%) constituted the majority reason for the referrals closely followed by disturbing behaviours [restlessness, n=63; 24.0% and aggression, n=47; 17.9% (Table 3)]. Schizophrenia/psychosis was the predominant diagnosis (n=37; 14.1%) and next was the diagnosis of depression (n=24; 9.1%) (Table 4). The majority of the referrals did not indicate psychiatry diagnosis (n=150; 57.0%) (Table 4).

Table 1: Referring departments

Department	Frequency	Percentage
Internal Medicine	123	46.8
Surgery	72	27.4
A&E	6	2.3
Obstetrics & gynaecology	30	11.4
Paediatrics	17	6.5
Pathology	5	1.9
Family medicine	3	1.1
Not specified	7	2.7
Total	263	100

Figure 1: Percentage of referrals from sub-specialty

Table 2: Duration spent with primary carer before referral

Duration	Frequency	Percent
<1 week	66	25.1
1-2 weeks	58	22.1
3-4 weeks	10	3.8
>4 weeks	28	10.6
Not stated	101	38.4
Total	263	100

Table 3: Reasons for the referral

Reason for Referral	Frequency (N = 263)	Percent (%)
Aggression	47	17.9%
Restlessness	63	24.0%
Sleep problem	17	6.5%
Sadness	32	12.2%
Irritability	32	12.2%
Hallucination	15	5.7%
Delusion	12	4.6%
Talkativeness	6	2.3%
Irrelevant speech	94	35.7%
Suicidality	16	6.1%
Alcohol Problem	9	3.4%
Substance use	20	7.6%
Confusion	38	14.4%
Forgetfulness	7	2.7%
Fearfulness	7	2.7%
Breathlessness	6	2.3%
Weakness	11	4.2%
Refusal to talk	16	6.1%
Anhedonia	17	6.5%
Refusal to eat/drink	25	9.5%
Somatic	10	3.8%
Others	1	0.4%
Total	263	100

Table 4: Diagnosis made by the referring department.

Diagnosis	Frequency	Percentage
Anxiety spectrum disorders	8	3.0
Depression	24	9.1
Bipolar	2	0.8
Schizophrenia/psychosis	37	14.1
Delirium	11	4.2
Dementia	8	3.0
Malingering	4	1.5
Seizure	5	1.9
Substance use disorder	11	4.2
Autism/ADHD	2	0.8
Not indicated	151	57.4
Total	263	100

DISCUSSION

This study set out to find the pattern of consultation-liaison psychiatry utilization in a multi-specialized tertiary hospital in south-eastern part of Nigeria. The

majority of the referrals to the Department of Mental Health were from the Department of Internal Medicine and the Department of Surgery. This is consistent with several literature reports where the

Department of Internal Medicine and Surgery were predominant in consultation-liaison psychiatry utilization in that order.^{7,8,12,13} The possible reason could be attributed to the higher number of patients with medically-unexplained somatic complaints attending medical outpatient clinic in tertiary hospitals. It may also reflect the complex pathophysiological interplay between chronic physical ailments and mental health disorders, where psychological components either exacerbate existing conditions or constitute primary concerns.¹⁴

Secondly, in this hospital, the resident doctors in the department of Internal Medicine are more likely to have more knowledge in psychiatry because they do compulsory residency posting in psychiatry, which makes them more capable of identifying patients in need of psychiatry care.

Concerning referrals from sub-specialties, studies have shown inconsistent results. Neurosurgery, Cardiology and Gastroenterology sub-specialties were the main sources of referral in our study. In contrast to findings from Acharjee *et al*¹⁵ in Bangladesh and Kumar *et al*,¹⁶ this showed that the majority of referrals/consults from sub-specialties in descending order are: Neurology-5.8%, Gastroenterology-5.3%, Burns & plastic surgery-3.0%, Orthopaedic-2.3%, Neurosurgery-1.9%, and Oncology- 1.0%, respectively. A cross-sectional study carried out in Nepal reported that Urology and Orthopaedics were the most common sources of the referrals.⁸ The heterogeneity in psychiatry training across centres, regions and specialties could be responsible for the varying results.¹⁷

Many studies reported different and several reasons for seeking psychiatry services for their patients.

However, the broad term 'abnormal behaviour' which may mean symptoms such as aggression, restlessness, irritability, etc., was prevalent across most studies, similar to our finding.^{7,8,18,19} Specifically, irrelevant speech and restlessness were the most common reasons for the referral in this study, probably because these are the early and frequent signs of medical illness-related factor such as delirium in medical wards, since most of the

referrals originated from the Department of Internal Medicine.²⁰ This is unlike what was reported in Indian studies where substance use and suicidal behaviours were the most prevailing specific reasons for their referrals.^{9,19,21}

More than half of the referrals did not state psychiatric diagnosis, as in other previous studies, though not in the same magnitude.^{7, 13} The possible low level of psychiatry knowledge or exposure among doctors in other specialties could account for the referrals without specifying a psychiatric diagnosis. However, in this study, among the psychiatric diagnoses made in the referrals/consults, schizophrenia/psychosis leads, followed by depressive disorders. This is in contrast to anxiety spectrum disorders and mood disorders reported in studies done in India⁷ and Nepal,⁸ but in consonance with Acharjee *et al.* in Bangladesh which reported schizophrenia as the commonest diagnosis stated in the referrals.¹⁵ Interesting to note, some literature evidence revealed substance use disorder as the most frequent diagnosis in their referrals.^{1,21} This divergence might point to regional differences in the presentation of psychological symptoms or variations in the clinical training and awareness of referring practitioners.

The implication of this study is that it gives a better understanding of the existing referral pattern in consultation-liaison psychiatry, and understanding these referral patterns is crucial for developing targeted interventions that improve inter-departmental collaboration and ultimately enhance patient care outcomes.

However, the retrospective design of this study presents notable limitations, chiefly the inability to ascertain causal factors contributing to the scanty referrals from many sub-specialties. Due to the nature of retrospective research, we were unable to collect primary data regarding attitudes, beliefs, or systemic factors influencing referral decisions. Additionally, the study's focus on a single tertiary hospital in Nigeria further limits the ability to extend findings universally across different healthcare facilities in the country. Future studies with a more

comprehensive, prospective approach could potentially reveal critical insights into departmental and systemic influences on referral patterns, thereby bridging gaps identified through this research's retrospective scope.

CONCLUSION

A noteworthy finding is that nearly half of the referrals originated from the Internal Medicine Department. The study also highlights that the predominant reasons prompting referrals to psychiatric services were irrelevant speech, followed by disturbing behaviours such as restlessness and aggression. This underscores a potential under-utilization of CLP from other specialties and may suggest a necessity for heightened awareness and training among non-psychiatric medical practitioners on identifying early mental ill-health signs that require a psychiatric evaluation.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declared no conflict of interest.

Authors' contribution statement

SOO, JUO, OKN, and RU were involved in conceptualisation, methodology, original drafting. OOO, SOO, MUM and EOO did the data analysis, curation and final drafting and editing. All authors approved the final editing.

Data availability statement

Data for this study will be made available when reasonably requested.

Disclaimer

The views and opinions expressed in this article are of the authors and do not reflect the official policy or position of any affiliated agency of the authors.

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